

Synthesis and Study of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Benzoylacetone with some Schiff Bases

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Several workers¹ reported mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with Schiff bases as bidentate ligands, and several reviews have appeared on metal β -diketone complexes². Hence, the above complexes from 2-hydroxy-5-carboxyacetophenone Schiff bases and benzoylacetone, have been studied.

Results and Discussion

The Ni^{II} complexes were found to be diamagnetic (Table 1). The conductivity measurements of the complexes revealed their non-electrolytic nature, giving low molar conductivity values.

TABLE I—DETAILS OF SCHIFF BASES AND COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Cu ^{II} complex		μ_{eff} B.M.	Ni ^{II} complex	
			Analysis % :			Analysis % :	
			Found/(Calcd.)			Found/(Calcd.)	
		N	Cu		N	Ni	
1.	H	H ₁	2.81 (2.92)	12.89 (13.27)	2.12	2.89 (2.97)	12.18 (12.39)
2.	H	Cl	2.65 (2.72)	12.17 (12.38)	2.05	2.61 (2.75)	11.02 (11.55)
3.	Cl	H	2.65 (2.72)	12.17 (12.28)	2.10	2.65 (2.75)	11.15 (11.55)
4.	NO ₂	Cl	4.95 (5.01)	11.17 (11.38)	2.11	5.0 (5.06)	10.28 (10.61)
5.	H	NO ₂	5.28 (5.34)	11.96 (12.13)	1.99	5.25 (5.39)	10.91 (11.31)
6.	NO ₂	H	5.29 (5.34)	11.94 (12.13)	1.97	5.25 (5.39)	11.17 (11.31)
7.	CH ₃	H	2.79 (2.84)	12.51 (12.90)	2.15	2.81 (2.87)	11.82 (12.03)
8.	Br	H	2.43 (2.51)	11.09 (11.40)	2.12	2.40 (2.53)	10.28 (10.62)
9.	MeO	H	2.33 (2.75)	12.20 (12.40)	2.02	2.65 (2.78)	11.18 (11.65)
10.	EtO	H	2.58 (2.68)	12.05 (12.16)	2.13	2.58 (2.70)	10.94 (11.34)
11.	NO ₂	MeO	4.98 (5.05)	11.20 (11.48)	2.12	5.02 (5.10)	10.71 (10.70)

The ligand ir band due to C=N (1 650 cm⁻¹) shifted to the lower side (1 600 cm⁻¹) on the complex formation. The ligand bands due to phenolic OH (1 200 cm⁻¹) disappeared in the complexes. These indicate coordination through azomethine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atom³. The bands due to enolic C=O in benzoylacetone (1 640 cm⁻¹) shifted to lower side (1 560 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, indicating coordination through C=O and involvement of enolic OH in the complex formation⁴.

On the basis of the above results, the complexes were assigned the following structure.

Experimental

A mixture of dry 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (13.8 g, 0.1 mol) and acetic anhydride (12.0 ml, 0.1 mol) containing a few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄, was heated in a water-bath for 1 h, then cooled and

treated with ice-cold water. The product 4-acetoxybenzoic acid (m.p. 189°) was converted into the corresponding hydroxyketone, HCAP (m.p. 240°) by Fries migration.

The Schiff bases were prepared by condensing HCAP with various arylamines according to the standard method⁵. HCAP (1.8 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol was mixed with the solution of amines (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled and treated with cold water to yield the product.

Mixed ligand complexes: The Schiff base in ethanol (50 ml, 0.01 mol) was mixed with benzoylacetone in ethanol (25 ml, 0.02 mol) and metal solution (10 ml, 0.05 mol) was then added dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture having a 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio, was vigorously stirred for 0.5 h at 50° and then refluxed for 1.5 h. The coloured complexes, separated on cooling, were filtered and washed with ethanol and hot water. The complexes formed in the pH range 6.5–7.5 for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were found to be insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in glacial acetic acid. The complexes were also found to be stable for weeks without any change.

The gravimetric determinations along with the metal content was determined by first decomposing the complex with HClO₄ and then titrating the solution with standard EDTA solution. Molecular weight was determined by Rast's method. The complexes were quantitatively analysed for their nitrogen content. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at 28°. Conductance of the complexes in glacial acetic acid was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge.

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